

IQTISODIYOT VA ZAMONAVIY TEXNOLOGIYA

Onlayn ilmiy jurnal

Jild: 04 Nashr: 02 (2025)

www.mudarrisziyo.uz

ISSN: 2992-8907

ADEQUATE FUNDING PANACEA FOR DEVELOPMENT OF CORRECTIONAL EDUCATION IN NIGERIA

Niyi Jacob Ogunode

Department of Education, University of Abuja, Nigeria

Conrad Ugochukwu Ukozor

Department of Educational Management, University of Abuja, Nigeria

Victor Olugbenga Ayoko

*Department of Educational Foundations, Faculty of Education, Open University of Faculty of
Education, National, Nigeria*

Ukpoju Bartholomew Ojochenemi

*Department of Educational Foundations & Management Studies, Kogi State College of
Education, Ankpa*

Abstract: *The paper discussed the important of adequately funding correctional education in Nigeria. The paper is a position paper. The paper employed the used of secondary data. The secondary data were collected from online and print resources. Content analysis was used to select the final literatures. The paper concluded that funding is vital to the development of correctional education in Nigeria. Adequate funding of correctional education in Nigeria will guarantee adequate funds for the management of correctional education, employment of adequate facilitators, provision of adequate infrastructure facilities, digitalization of correctional education and ensure provision of instructional resources. Based on this, this paper hereby recommends that the government should increase the budgetary allocation to the correctional education. Private institutions and religious organizations should provide financial support to correctional education. Government agencies and stakeholders in correctional education should ensure effective supervision of correctional education to ensure quality in the system.*

Keywords: *Correctional education, Education, Funding.*

Introduction

Education is a process that transfer knowledge, skills, and character traits that comes or manifests in various forms to empower the individual to be social and economic useful to himself or herself and the society. Education is an organized and planned process that leads to acquisition of knowledge from an institute of learning for personal and national development (Ogunode, Solomon, & Idonigie, 2024). Education is the sum-total of all experiences that students receive either in the school or outside the school. This implies that whatever that broadens our horizon, deepens our insight, refines individual reactions and stimulates thoughts and feelings educate us. So, education is a lifelong process. Life –long education implies that education is a process which goes on from birth to death. Education involves both formal and non-formal type of education. Non-formal

education is organized outside the school system and geared towards addressing the problems of specific target groups in the society, especially those adults and students who for one reason or the other had their basic education interrupted. It is the development of all those capacities in the individual, which will enable him to control his environment and fulfill his possibilities. Hence the need to assess implementation of universal basic education for attainment of educational goals (Nweke, Alumode, Umahi, & Ikechukwu 2022).

Education is the process whereby a human being gradually adopts himself in various ways to his physical, social, and spiritual environments (Onwubiuko, 2012). Education is regarded as that which is given to an individual to make him develop socially, morally, and intellectually as to allow for his or her personal overall development and the development of the community in which he finds himself. This implies that education whether formal or non-formal is goal oriented. Education should be functional, qualitative and socio-personal in the sense that it must be tailored toward serving the society and the personality involved (Ozochi 2009). Education is the process through which individuals are made participating members of their society. It is the system through which man becomes moral agent capable of living in society and contributing towards the growth and development of the society. It is the process through which the young acquires the ability to be useful to himself and others. It is also a process through which man realises his potentialities and uses it for self-fulfillment in the service of himself and others (Unknown).

Education takes different forms such as economic education, green education, physics education, formal education, non-formal education, correctional education. Correctional education is the education in the correctional centres. Correctional education is an organized education designed to provide educational services for inmates in correctional centres with the aims of empowering the inmates after jail term. Correctional education like every other forms of education in Nigeria is faced with the problem of poor funding. Ogunode, Edinoh, and Odo, (2023) noted that inadequate funding of correctional education in Nigeria has resulted to deterioration of physical facilities; shortage of instructional resources, dearth of quality scientific research and inadequate ICT facilities in the various centres. Funding is key to correctional education development in Nigeria. Ayeni and Babalola (2009) concluded that funding was central and germane to the success at all levels of education. Ogbonnaya (2000) noted that funds are necessary for staff payment, staff development and procurement of educational materials, which in themselves are indices of effective management.

Adequate funding refer to the provision of financial resources that is sufficient to execute the programme or projects. Adequate funding in education connote official provision of funds that are enough for the implementation of education programmes. Adequate funding can also be seen as a situation whereby there are enough provision for funds for the execution of educational projects or programme within a year. Adequate funding is critical for the development of any public institution. Adequate funding is the key to the achievement of the institution's goals. Adequate funding is the life wire of any organization (Ogunode, Ukozor, & Ayoko, 2023). No meaningful impact educational institutions can attain without adequate funding. It is based on this that this paper seeks to explore the importance of adequately funding correctional education in Nigeria.

Literature Review

Correctional Education

Prison education, also known as Inmate Education and Correctional Education, is an expansive term encompassing any educational activities occurring inside a prison. These educational activities

include both vocational training and academic education. The goal of such activities is to prepare the prisoner for success outside of prison and to enhance the rehabilitative aspects of prison. Educational programs offered inside prisons are typically provided and managed by the prison systems in which they reside. Funding for the programs is provided through official correctional department budgets, private organizations (e.g., colleges, nonprofits, etc.), and the prisoners or their families if the prisoner is pursuing education through a correspondence program. Educational opportunities can be divided into two general categories: academic education and vocational training (Zoukis, 2011). Wood (2020) noted that prison education programs help lower recidivism rates and increase employment opportunities post-release.

The objectives of educational programmes to Inmates according to Ajufo, et al, (Undated) include; to improve inmates' academic and vocational skills; to assist inmates in becoming responsible and productive citizens in the society; to change inmates' attitudes regarding work and responsibility; to prepare inmates for the competitive job market they will face upon release; to promote inmates' self-confidence which will stand them in good stead when they leave prison and to prepare inmates for a successful life after release from prison. For Ogbaka et al., (2017) there are three main objectives of prison education at the primary level, which cut across different views of the purpose of the criminal justice system. These include keeping inmates meaningfully busy, causing a change in their attitude and behavior, and opening up employment opportunities through vocational skills, further education, and training. Education has a key role in rehabilitating prisoners into the society and helping them to secure employment. With 80 percent of prisoners functionally illiterate, the best crime prevention programme of all is education. Educational programme is a necessary viable and positive component of the rehabilitation programme for inmates since it does not involve additional security risks (Ajufo, et al Undated).

Education of the inmates in the prison yard is a necessity for two reasons. Firstly, every eligible citizen of Nigeria has right to education, Incarceration in the prison cannot erode such right in as much as the citizenship of such inmates is not questionable. Secondly, Learning is only possible through Education. If prison is to serve actually correctional function of the life of the inmates, education in the prison is important and should gain the attention of the government. Knowledge is acquired or imparted through education. The inmates need to be trained toward correcting some of the fundamental blunder or notion imbibed in life that put them into problem (Ajufo, & Osiyemi, Undated). From the above, correctional education is an education that takes place in the prison with the purpose of providing quality education for inmates to ensure that they are useful after their prison term. Correctional education encompass all teaching and learning programme taking place in the prison to provide skills and knowledge to inmate so that they can be useful to the community after their release for the prison. Correctional education is an organized education designed for inmates with the aims of providing them an employable skills that can make them contribute to the society after the completion of their jail. Correctional education is a prison education that is provided to all inmates for the purpose of providing access to human right and equalization of educational opportunities.

The objectives of correctional education includes; to provide quality education for inmates; to provide skills and improve the knowledge of inmates; to provide continuous education opportunities for inmates; to inspire its inmates with a desire for self-improvement and achievement of excellence; to foster national unity with an emphasis on the common ties that unite us in our diversity; to provide all primary school leavers with the opportunity for education of a secondary education level, irrespective of sex, social status, religion or ethnic background; to provide all

secondary school leavers with the opportunity for higher education, to offer a sound and diversified curriculum to cater for the differences in talents, opportunities and future roles in the society; and to provide manpower training in the applied science, technology and commerce at sub-professional grades for inmates.

Method

This paper explores and explores the importance of adequately funding correctional education in Nigeria. Data from different secondary sources were employed for the paper. The paper used content analysis to analyze all the literature collected. Only those relevant to the topic were systematically selected. The exploratory method was adopted in the analysis. To ensure the reliability and validity of the study, multiple secondary sources were used to minimize the risk of error. The secondary data were collected directly from textbooks, journals, articles, newspapers and other local and international publications on sexual harassment in tertiary institutions (adapted from Ogunode & Ukozo, 2023).

Data Analysis

Discussion on adequate funding panacea for development of correctional education in Nigeria

Funding is vital for the development of correctional education. Adequate funding of correctional education in Nigeria will guarantee sufficient funds for the administration of prison education. Adequate funding will ensure procurement of both human and materials resources needed for the implementation of curriculum in correctional centres. Adequate funding will permit educational institutions in Nigeria to have enough for school administration and management and to meet up with unforeseen circumstance (Ibara, 2011; Nwafor, Uchendu, & Akani, 2015).

Adequate funding of correctional centres in Nigeria will help to fix the problem of shortage facilities or instructors in the various centres. Sarkinfada, and Garba, (2023) noted that one of the problem facing prison education in Nigeria is shortage of professional facilitators. This problem have hindered the development of prison education. Funding of correctional education will help to employ adequate facilitators or instructors in the various centres across the country. Facilitators are professional employed to providing teaching services in the correctional centres. Only adequate funding of education in Nigeria will guarantee adequate employment of teachers and facilities in the correctional centres (Akinsanya, 2007; Ogunode, Ukozor, & Ayoko, 2023; Ogunode, Olowonefa, & Suleiman, 2023).

Adequate funding of correctional centres in Nigeria will facilitate and aid provision of capacity building programme for the facilitators. Capacity building takes place on an individual level, institutional level and societal level. On an individual level, it requires the development of conditions that allow individual participants to build and enhance existing knowledge and skills. It also calls for the establishment of conditions that will allow individuals to engage in the process of learning and adapting to change. On an institutional level, it involves aiding pre-existing institutions and supporting them in forming sound policies, organisational structures and effective method of management (United Nations Committee of Experts on Public Administration 2006). Capacity building is a process of developing and strengthening the skills, instincts, abilities, processes and resources that individuals, organisations and communities need to survive, adapt and thrive in the fast changing world (Philbin 1996). Capacity building is key for the total development of teachers and facilitators in teaching in the correctional centres (United Nations Environment Programme 2006; UN 2020; Pierro, 2020). Adequate funding of education, according to Agabi,

(2014) and Ololube, (2013) guarantee staff development through academic programs like workshops, seminars, conferences, and scholarships. Most importantly, staff welfare and retention through regular payment of staff salaries and allowances assured. It guarantee's the protection of students welfare by providing playgrounds, refectories, lavatories, hostels, resource centers, etc.; and the maintenance of healthy schooling environment via good sanitary environment, avert multiple disciplinary problems, regular maintenance, etc..

Adequate funding of correctional centres in Nigeria help to solve the problem of infrastructural facilities shortage in the various correctional centres in Nigeria. School Infrastructural facilities according Ogunode and Agwor (2021) opined refer to social capital within the school environment. They include school buildings/complexes such as: classrooms, tables, exam halls, chairs, auditoria, desks, staff offices, seminar/conference/board rooms, laboratories, workshops, studios, farms, gymnasia, central libraries, specialized/professional libraries, faculty libraries, departmental libraries, etc; Institute/centres' specialized facilities such as: ICT infrastructure, special laboratories, conference facilities, etc; lecture Boards such as: interactive, magnetic, screen and chalk, etc; ICT facilities such as: computer laboratories and services, network connectivity, multi-media system, public address system, slide, and video projectors, and Ergonomics furnishing in laboratories, libraries, and lecture rooms/theatres, moot courts, and studios, etc; Students' hostels or accommodations including: Boys and Girls hostels; and municipal/physical infrastructure such as: power supply, water supply, good road networks, sports, health and sanitation, staff schools, security facilities, etc. Adequate funding of education in Nigeria will guarantee development of facilities in schools (Anike, & Tari, 2011; Ogunode & Mohammed, 2023; Ogunode, Olaoye, & Yakubu, 2023). Also, Ololube et al., (2016a) and Onyekwena, Uzor, Oloko, and Adeniran (undated) posited that if education institutions are adequately funded, it creates room for better infrastructural development and maintenance of school buildings, office blocks, classroom blocks, student hostels, staff quarter, etc.

Adequate funding of correctional centres in Nigeria help to digitalize the correctional centres in Nigeria. Digitalization is the act of transforming information data into digital format for easy transmission that support effectiveness and efficiency in service delivery in an organization. Digitalization involves the process of converting analog information into digital formats through the use of digital tools to enhance services delivery in organization. Digitalization in education according to Ogunode, Olowonefa and Ukozor (2025) is the process of utilizing digital technologies to practically implement the school curriculum. Digitalization involves moving from manual model of carrying out services into digital model by deploying technological resources. Digitalization of correctional centres in Nigeria can only be possible through adequate funding. Digitalization of correctional education will help to deliver quality education in the centres. Digitalization in the centres will support improved learning and improved facilitators' job performance. Ogunode, et al (2025) digitalization of basic education that also include correctional centres in Nigeria will fundamentally transform the correctional education and increase access to prison education and improving teaching and learning delivery in the schools. Specifically, education digitalization provides the following opportunities; personalized learning model, virtual learning, smart classroom model, blended learning and online learning.

Adequate funding of correctional centres in Nigeria help to provide adequate instructional resources in the correctional centres in Nigeria. Fadeyiye (2005) viewed instructional materials as visual and audio-visual aids, concrete or non-concrete, used by teachers to improve the quality of teaching and learning activities in schools. Ibeneme (2000) defined teaching aids as those materials used for

practical and demonstration in the classroom by students and teachers while Ikerionwu (2000) defined instructional materials as objects or devices that assist the teacher to present a lesson to the learners in a logical manner. Okhakhu, Oladiran, and Omoike, (2016); Onykwelu, (1995); Oluwagbohunmi and Abdul-Raheem (2014) opined that instructional materials are used by teachers to aid explanations and make the learning of subject matter understandable to students during the teaching-learning process. Abdu-Raheem (2016) stated that instructional materials are essential and significant tools needed for teaching and learning school subjects to promote teachers' efficiency and improve students' performance. They make learning more interesting, practical, realistic and appealing. They also enable both the teachers and students to participate actively and effectively in lesson sessions. It enables the procurement of instructional materials or resources like medical tools, books and journals for libraries, electronic boards, computers, laboratory equipment, video conferencing facilities, etc. (Ololube, Agbor, Major, Agabi & Wali, 2016c; Sanni 2016).

Findings

The paper concluded that funding is vital to the development of correctional education in Nigeria. Adequate funding of correctional education in Nigeria will guarantee adequate funds for the management of correctional education, employment of adequate facilitators, provision of adequate infrastructure facilities, digitalization of correctional education and ensure provision of instructional resources.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The paper concluded that funding is vital to the development of correctional education in Nigeria. Adequate funding of correctional education in Nigeria will guarantee adequate funds for the correctional education management, ensure employment of adequate facilitators, provide adequate infrastructure facilities, support digitalization of correctional education and ensure provision of instructional resources.

Based on this, this paper hereby recommends that the government should increase the budgetary allocation to the correctional education. Private institutions and religious organizations should provide financial support to correctional education. Government agencies and stakeholders in correctional education should ensure effective supervision of correctional education to ensure quality in the system.

References

1. Abdu-Raheem, B. O. (2016) Effects of Instructional Materials on Secondary Schools Students' Academic Achievement in Social Studies in Ekiti State, Nigeria. *World Journal of Education*, 6, (1) 32-39.
2. Ajah, B., O & Joshua O. N. (2017) Challenges Facing Vocational Training of Prison Inmates in Nigeria: A Study of Abakaliki and Awka Prisons. *Middle-East Journal of Scientific Research* 25 (7): 1458-1468.
3. Agabi, C. O. (2014). *Teaching and resources management in education*. Port Harcourt: Rodi Printing and Publishing.
4. Akinsanya, O. O. (2007). Financing higher education in Nigeria. *International Journal of African & African American Studies*, VI(1), 68-72.
5. Ajufo, B. I. & Osiyemi, A. J, (Undated) Education in the prison Yard in Nigeria.

6. Aliyu, K., Mustaffa, J., & Nasir, N. M. (2016). An evaluation of prison educational programmes in Kwara State Nigeria. *Association of Sociologists of Education of Nigeria*, 8(1), 103–
7. Anike, L. and Tari, G. (2011). Provision and management of school facilities for the implementation of UBE programme. *Journal of Education and Social Research*, 1(4): 33 - 45.120.
8. Ayeni A.O and Babalola J.B (2009). *Funding Options for Educational Inventions in the Educational Sector Ibadan-his lineage publishing house.*
9. Fadeiye, J.O. (2005). *A social studies textbook for colleges and universities.* Ibadan: Akin-Johnson Press and Publishers.
10. Ibara, E. G. (2011). Funding higher education in a dwindling fiscal resources allocation: the Nigerian perspective. *Journal of Sustainable Development in Africa*, 13(3), 1-9.
11. Ibeneme, O.T. (2000). Provision and utilization of instructional equipment for teaching and learning science and technology. *Issues in Educational Journal*, 1, 139-144.
12. Isola, O.M. (2010). Effect of standardized and improvised instructional materials on students' academic achievement in secondary school physics. Unpublished M. Ed. project, University of Ibadan, Ibadan.
13. Nweke, C., Alumode, B.E. Umahi, N, A. & Ikechukwu F., C. (2022). Extent of Implementation of Universal Basic Education Programme In South-East Nigeria. *Unizik Journal of Educational Research and Policy Studies*, 14 (3), 187-197.
14. Nwafor, N. E. Uchendu, E. E & Akani, C. O (2015) Need for adequate funding in the Administration of secondary education in Nigeria. *Global Journal of Educational Research*, (14), 119-124
15. Ogonnaya, N. I. (2000). *Foundation of education finance.* Onitsha: CAP Publishers.
16. Ogunode, N. J. & Agwor O., J. (2021). Perception of Secondary school teachers on the causes of inadequate infrastructural facilities in public secondary schools in Gwagwalada Area Council of F.C.T, Abuja, Nigeria. *Electronic Research Journal of Behavioural Sciences*, 4 (2021), 1-9
17. Ogunode, N. J. & Ukozo, C. U (2023). Exploring alternative funding options for universities education in a depressed economy. *Fan, Ta'lim, Madaniyat Va Innovatsiya*, 2(10), 64-76. <https://mudarrisziyo.uz/index.php/innovatsiya/article/view/451>
18. Ogunode, N., J., Solomon, A., T & Idonigie, A (2024). The Impact of Economic Hardship on Education in Nigeria. *American Journal of Management Practice*, 1(6), 61-69
19. Ogunode, N. J. ., Ukozor, C. U. ., & Udejaja, P. C. . (2025). Green Church Initiative in Nigeria. *Spanish Journal of Innovation and Integrity*, 38, 175–185. Retrieved from <https://sjii.es/index.php/journal/article/view/200>
20. Ogunode, N, J., Olowonefa J., A, & Ukozor. C., U. (2025). Basic Education Digitalization in Nigeria: Implication for Administrative Decision Making. *International Journal of Formal Education*, 4(2), 1–7. Retrieved from <https://journals.academiczone.net/index.php/ijfe/article/view/4430>

21. Ogunode N, J., Ukozor, C., U. & Ayoko, V., O (2023). Adequate Funding of National Universities Commission for Effective Universities Supervision in Nigeria. *Journal of economics, finance and Innovation* 2(1), 1-10
22. Ogunode, N. J. Olowonefa, J. A & Suleiman, S (2023) Benefits of Funding Tertiary Education in Nigeria. *European Journal of Artificial Intelligence and Digital Economy*, 1(3), 5-16
23. Ogunode, N., J., Azarema, I., Ukozor, C., U. (2024). Adequate Funding Panacea for the Development of Teachers' Education in Nigeria. *American Journal of Education and Evaluation Studies*, 1(1), 1-7.
24. Ogunode, N. J., & Mohammed, Y. D. (2023). Adequate funding: Panacea for development of educational administration and planning programme in tertiary institutions in Nigeria. *Pubmedia Social Sciences and Humanities*, 1(3), 1–13.
25. Ogunode, N. J., Olaoye, A. E., & Yakubu, I. (2023). Adequate funding of public universities and effective implementation of core curriculum and minimum academic standards (CCMAS) in North-East, Nigeria universities. *Analytical Journal of Education and Development*, 3(3), 215–222.
26. Ogunode, N. J. ., Edinoh, K. ., & Odo, R. C. . (2023). Development of Tertiary Education in Prison and Correctional Centres in Nigeria. *Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development*, 2(6), 301–310. Retrieved from <https://www.bjisrd.com/index.php/bjisrd/article/view/335>
27. Ogunode N, J., Ukozor, C., U. & Ayoko, V., O (2023). Adequate Funding of National Universities Commission for Effective Universities Supervision in Nigeria. *Journal of economics, finance and Innovation* 2(1), 1-10
28. Okhakhu, D. O, Oladiran, M. D & Omoike, D. A (2016) Instructional materials as determinants of students' academic performance at the secondary school level In Ikorodu local government, Lagos State, Nigeria. *Journal of Information and Knowledge Management*, 7, (1).
29. Oluwagbohunmi, M.F., & Abdu-Raheem, B.O. (2014) Sandwich undergraduates' problem of improvisation of instructional materials in social studies: The case of Ekiti State University. *Journal of International Academic Research for Multidisciplinary*, 1(12), 824-831
30. Ololube, N. P., Ololube, D. O., & Aiya, F. (2016a). Investing in building resilient infrastructures, promoting inclusive and sustainable industrialization to foster innovation through effective higher education. *Journal of Global Economics, management and Business Research*, 7(4), 257-273.
31. Ololube, N. P., Agbor, C. N., Major, N. B., Agabi C. O., & Wali, W. I. (2016c). 2015 global information technology report: consequences on knowledge management in higher education institutions in Nigeria. *International Journal of Education and Development Using ICT*, 12(2), 4-25.
32. Ololube, N. P. (2013). *Educational management, planning and supervision: model for effective implementation*. Owerri, Nigeria: Springfield Publishers.
33. Ololube, N. P., Aiya, F., Uriah, O. A., & Ololube, D. O. (2016d). Strategic planning: a universal remedy for the successful management of 21st century university education (UE). *Management*, 6(3), 76-88. DOI:10.5923/j.mm.20160603.03.

34. Onasanya, S.A., & Omosewo, E.O. (2011). Effect of improvised and standard instructional materials on secondary school student's academic performance in Physics in Ilorin, Nigeria. *Singapore Journal of Scientific Research*, 1(1), 68-76. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3923/sjsres.2011.68.76>
35. Onykwelu, G. N. (1995). Availability and Utilization of Educational Media in the Teaching of History in Secondary Schools in Anambra State. Unpublished M. Ed. Thesis U.N.N
36. Onyekwena, C. Uzor, E. Oloko, T. & Adeniran, A (undated) Financing Basic Education in Nigeria. What is the feasible option? Centre for the study of economies of Africa, Abuja Nigeria.
37. Onwubuiko, G. (2012). Implementation of the Universal Basic Education Programme in the South-East and South-South geopolitical zones. *Unpublished Masters thesis* submitted to the Department of Arts Education, University of Nigeria, Nsukka.
38. Ozochi, B. A. (2009). Achieving Universals Basic Education in Nigeria: Strategies for Improved Funding and Cost Effectiveness. *The Social Sciences*, 2(3), 342-345.
39. Pierro, G. D (2020). Capacity building: is it only a matter of training? <https://www.learlab.com/insights/capacity-building-is-it-only-a-matter-of-training/>
40. Philbin, A. (1996). *Capacity Building in Social Justice Organization*. New York: Ford Foundations.
41. Sanni A (2016). Cost and alternative sources of financing university education in Nigeria retrieve from Scholar.google.com on 4/1/16
42. Sarkinfada, H. ., & Garba, A. D. . (2023). Prison Education or Correctional Education in Nigeria. *Modern Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 2(6), 21–27. <https://doi.org/10.51699/mjssh.v2i6.653>
43. Vidal, C (2023). What is digitalization in education? https://www.pfu-us.ricoh.com/blog/digitalization-in-education?srsltid=AfmBOopm580klm5j_idFG2ziiRt_lrhtcf0k7UyxWt7yJR30xT0wUMa
44. United Nations Committee of Experts on Public Administration (2006). *United Nations' Economic and Social Council: Delimitation of Basic Concepts and Terminologies in Government and Public Administration*. Retrieved from <http://unpanl.un.org/intradoc/groups/public/documents>.
45. United Nations Environment Programme (2006). *Ways to Increase the Effectiveness of Capacity Building for Sustainable Development*. Discussion Paper Presented at The Concurrent Session 18.1: The Marrakesh Action Plan and Follow Up. 1A1A Annual Conference, Stavanger, Norway.
46. UN (2020) What is capacity building? <https://www.un.org/en/academic-impact/capacity-building>
- Zoukis, C. (2011). What is Prison Education and Why Should We Care? <https://federalcriminaldefenseattorney.com/what-is-prison-education-and-why-should-we-care-html/>